

Google cloud training Notes

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- Create a VM from compute engine, VM instances.
- You can create a VM instance from gcloud console or from gcloud command line.
- Commands used when creating a VM from gcloud command line:
 - o gcloud config set
 - o gcloud config get-value
 - o gcloud compute
 - o Gcloud logging
- Three basic ways to interact with Google Cloud services and resources are:
 - o Command-line interface
 - o Client libraries
 - o Cloud Console
- GKE cluster features:
 - o Load balancing for Compute Engine instances
 - o Node pools to designate subsets of nodes within a cluster for additional flexibility
 - o Automatic scaling of your cluster's node instance count
 - o Automatic upgrades for your cluster's node software
 - o Node auto-repair to maintain node health and availability
 - o Logging and Monitoring with Cloud Monitoring for visibility into your cluster
- To create GKE cluster used the following commands:
 - o Gcloud container
 - o For other commands check "Introduction to containers kubernetes and openshift" in the kubernetes part

To create an HTTP LoadBalancer with nginx servers use the following:

- gcloud config set project qwiklabs-gcp-04-255d82868b9c
- gcloud config set compute/zone us-central1-a
- gcloud config set compute/region us-central1
- Nano startup.sh copy the script into the file and save it.
- The script: "#! /bin/bash
apt-get update
apt-get install -y nginx
service nginx start
sed -i -- 's/nginx/Google Cloud Platform - ""\$HOSTNAME""/' /var/www/html/index.nginx-debian.html"
- gcloud compute instance-templates create instancetemplate \--machine-type e2-medium \--metadata-from-file=startup-script=startup.sh

- `gcloud compute target-pools create targetpool`
- `gcloud compute instance-groups managed create instancegroup --zone us-central1-a --template instancetemplate --size 2 --target-pool targetpool`
- `gcloud compute instance-groups managed set-named-ports instancegroup \--named-ports http:80`
- `gcloud compute firewall-rules create grant-tcp-rule-390 --allow=tcp:80 --source-ranges="130.211.0.0/22,35.191.0.0/16" --direction=INGRESS`
- `gcloud compute addresses create ipaddress \--ip-version=IPV4 \--global`
- `gcloud compute health-checks create http healthcheck --check-interval 5s --unhealthy-threshold 2 --global --port=80 --autohealing`
- `gcloud compute backend-services create backendservice --health-checks=healthcheck --protocol=http --global`
- `gcloud compute backend-services add-backend backendservice --instance-group=instancegroup --global`
- `gcloud compute url-maps create urlmap --default-service=backendservice`
- `gcloud compute target-http-proxies create proxyurlmap --url-map=urlmap`
- `gcloud compute forwarding-rules create forwardingrule --target-http-proxy=proxyurlmap --global --ports=80`

End of the HTTP LoadBalancer.

Vertex AI: what been done in the vertex lab was:

- Create Vertex AI custom service account for Vertex Tensorboard integration
- Deploy a notebook instance
- Clone a repository
- Install dependencies after enabling them.

Dataprep:

- Created a dataprep from the cloud console.
- And created a flow in the dataprep.
- Then importing dataset from cloud storage.
- And start applying formulas and transformations to the recipes

Dataflow Templates:

- Create a BigQuery dataset and table using the cloud console and the cloud shell
- And create a bucket and
- Then run a pipeline where a pipeline means creating a dataflow and a job in the dataflow

Dataprocc:

- Create a spark-hadoop cluster
- Run a spark job

Cloud Natural Language API:

- First create an API key
- Make an entity analysis request

Cloud Speech API:

- Create an API key
- Create a speech API request, and that is by creating a json file and adding the following to it:
 - o The request body (json file) has a config and audio object.
 - o In config, you tell the Speech API how to process the request.
 - The encoding parameter tells the API which type of audio encoding you're using while the file is being sent to the API.
 - FLAC is the encoding type for .raw files.
- Call the speech API

Video intelligence:

- Enable "cloud video intelligence API"
- Set up authorization
- Create a video request

Challenge lab for data, ML, AI:

- To finish the lab it looks like I need to know how to create the schema or create one manually, and in the AI part I need to know how to upload the result

Challenge lab of Create ML Models with BigQuery ML(draft):

Create a model to predict new bicycle models, first model works on the features:

- the start station,
- the location of the start station,
- the day of the week
- the hour the trip started.

While the features for the second model:

- start station,
- subscriber type,
- the hour the trip started.

- To create a training dataset:

////////////////////////////////////

```
#standardSQL
```

```
WITH params AS (
```

```
  SELECT
```

```
    1 AS TRAIN,
```

```
    2 AS EVAL
```

```
  ),
```

```
daynames AS
```

```
(SELECT ['Sun', 'Mon', 'Tues', 'Wed', 'Thurs', 'Fri', 'Sat'] AS daysofweek),
```

```
taxitrips AS (
```

```
  SELECT
```

```
(tolls_amount + fare_amount) AS total_fare,
```

```
daysofweek[ORDINAL(EXTRACT(DAYOFWEEK FROM pickup_datetime))] AS dayofweek,
```

```
EXTRACT(HOUR FROM pickup_datetime) AS hourofday,
```

```
pickup_longitude AS pickuplon,
```

```
pickup_latitude AS pickuplat,
```

```

dropoff_longitude AS dropofflon,
dropoff_latitude AS dropofflat,
passenger_count AS passengers
FROM
`nyc-tlc.yellow.trips`, daynames, params
WHERE
trip_distance > 0 AND fare_amount > 0
AND MOD(ABS(FARM_FINGERPRINT(CAST(pickup_datetime AS STRING))),1000) =
params.TRAIN
)
SELECT *
FROM taxitrips

```

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- To create a bigquery dataset to store models:

////////////////////////////////////

1. In the left-hand *Explorer* panel, click on the **View actions** icon next to your Project ID and then click **Create dataset**.
2. In the Create Dataset dialog, enter in the following:
 - For **Dataset ID**, type **taxi**.
 - Select **us(multiple regions in United States)** as the **Data location**
 - Leave the other values at their defaults.
3. Then click **Create dataset**.

////////////////////////////////////

- To create a bigquery model:

////////////////////////////////////

```

CREATE or REPLACE MODEL taxi.taxifare_model
OPTIONS
(model_type='linear_reg', labels=['total_fare']) AS
WITH params AS (
SELECT
1 AS TRAIN,
2 AS EVAL

```

```

),
daynames AS
  (SELECT ['Sun', 'Mon', 'Tues', 'Wed', 'Thurs', 'Fri', 'Sat'] AS daysofweek),
taxitrips AS (
SELECT
  (tolls_amount + fare_amount) AS total_fare,
  daysofweek[ORDINAL(EXTRACT(DAYOFWEEK FROM pickup_datetime))] AS dayofweek,
  EXTRACT(HOUR FROM pickup_datetime) AS hourofday,
  pickup_longitude AS pickuplon,
  pickup_latitude AS pickuplat,
  dropoff_longitude AS dropofflon,
  dropoff_latitude AS dropofflat,
  passenger_count AS passengers
FROM
  `nyc-tlc.yellow.trips`, daynames, params
WHERE
  trip_distance > 0 AND fare_amount > 0
  AND MOD(ABS(FARM_FINGERPRINT(CAST(pickup_datetime AS STRING))),1000) = params.TRAIN
)
SELECT *
FROM taxitrips
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%

OR
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%

#standardSQL
CREATE OR REPLACE MODEL `bqml_lab.sample_model`
OPTIONS(model_type='logistic_reg') AS
SELECT
  IF(totals.transactions IS NULL, 0, 1) AS label,
  IFNULL(device.operatingSystem, "") AS os,

```

```

device.isMobile AS is_mobile,
IFNULL(geoNetwork.country, "") AS country,
IFNULL(totals.pageviews, 0) AS pageviews
FROM
`bigquery-public-data.google_analytics_sample.ga_sessions_*`
WHERE
  _TABLE_SUFFIX BETWEEN '20160801' AND '20170631'
LIMIT 100000;

```

```

////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////

```

```

- Model evaluation:

```

```

////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////

```

```

#standardSQL

```

```

SELECT
  SQRT(mean_squared_error) AS rmse
FROM
  ML.EVALUATE(MODEL taxi.taxifare_model,
  (
  WITH params AS (
    SELECT
      1 AS TRAIN,
      2 AS EVAL
  ),
  daynames AS
    (SELECT ['Sun', 'Mon', 'Tues', 'Wed', 'Thurs', 'Fri', 'Sat'] AS daysofweek),
  taxitrips AS (
  SELECT
    (tolls_amount + fare_amount) AS total_fare,
    daysofweek[ORDINAL(EXTRACT(DAYOFWEEK FROM pickup_datetime))] AS dayofweek,
    EXTRACT(HOUR FROM pickup_datetime) AS hourofday,
    pickup_longitude AS pickuplon,

```

```

pickup_latitude AS pickuplat,
dropoff_longitude AS dropofflon,
dropoff_latitude AS dropofflat,
passenger_count AS passengers
FROM
`nyc-tlc.yellow.trips`, daynames, params
WHERE
trip_distance > 0 AND fare_amount > 0
AND MOD(ABS(FARM_FINGERPRINT(CAST(pickup_datetime AS STRING))),1000) = params.EVAL
)
SELECT *
FROM taxitrips
))
////////////////////////////////////

OR
////////////////////////////////////

#standardSQL
SELECT
*
FROM
ml.EVALUATE(MODEL `bqml_lab.sample_model`, (
SELECT
IF(totals.transactions IS NULL, 0, 1) AS label,
IFNULL(device.operatingSystem, "") AS os,
device.isMobile AS is_mobile,
IFNULL(geoNetwork.country, "") AS country,
IFNULL(totals.pageviews, 0) AS pageviews
FROM
`bigquery-public-data.google_analytics_sample.ga_sessions_*`
WHERE

```

```
_TABLE_SUFFIX BETWEEN '20170701' AND '20170801'));
```

```
////////////////////////////////////
```

```
- To predict
```

```
////////////////////////////////////
```

```
#standardSQL
```

```
SELECT
```

```
*
```

```
FROM
```

```
ml.PREDICT(MODEL `taxi.taxifare_model`,
```

```
(
```

```
WITH params AS (
```

```
SELECT
```

```
1 AS TRAIN,
```

```
2 AS EVAL
```

```
),
```

```
daynames AS
```

```
(SELECT ['Sun', 'Mon', 'Tues', 'Wed', 'Thurs', 'Fri', 'Sat'] AS daysofweek),
```

```
taxitrips AS (
```

```
SELECT
```

```
(tolls_amount + fare_amount) AS total_fare,
```

```
daysofweek[ORDINAL(EXTRACT(DAYOFWEEK FROM pickup_datetime))] AS dayofweek,
```

```
EXTRACT(HOUR FROM pickup_datetime) AS hourofday,
```

```
pickup_longitude AS pickuplon,
```

```
pickup_latitude AS pickuplat,
```

```
dropoff_longitude AS dropofflon,
```

```
dropoff_latitude AS dropofflat,
```

```
passenger_count AS passengers
```

```
FROM
```

```
`nyc-tlc.yellow.trips`, daynames, params
```

```
WHERE
```

```
trip_distance > 0 AND fare_amount > 0
AND MOD(ABS(FARM_FINGERPRINT(CAST(pickup_datetime AS STRING))),1000) = params.EVAL
)
SELECT *
FROM taxitrips
));
```

```
////////////////////////////////////
```

```
OR
```

```
////////////////////////////////////
```

```
#standardSQL
```

```
SELECT
  country,
  SUM(predicted_label) as total_predicted_purchases
FROM
  ml.PREDICT(MODEL `bqml_lab.sample_model`, (
SELECT
  IFNULL(device.operatingSystem, "") AS os,
  device.isMobile AS is_mobile,
  IFNULL(totals.pageviews, 0) AS pageviews,
  IFNULL(geoNetwork.country, "") AS country
FROM
  `bigquery-public-data.google_analytics_sample.ga_sessions_`
WHERE
  _TABLE_SUFFIX BETWEEN '20170701' AND '20170801'))
GROUP BY country
ORDER BY total_predicted_purchases DESC
LIMIT 10;
```

```
////////////////////////////////////
```

```
Latest try:
```

```
#standardSQL
```

```

CREATE OR REPLACE MODEL `bicycles.first_model`
OPTIONS(model_type='linear_reg') as
SELECT
start_station_name AS start_station,
address AS location_start_station,
EXTRACT(HOUR FROM start_time) AS hourofday
FROM
`bigquery-public-data.austin_bikeshare.bikeshare_stations`
FULL OUTER JOIN `bigquery-public-data.austin_bikeshare.bikeshare_trips` ON `bigquery-public-
data.austin_bikeshare.bikeshare_stations`.station_id=`bigquery-public-data.austin_bikeshare.bikeshare_trips`.start_station_id

```

////////////////////////////////////

The ones that worked:

- First model:

#standardSQL

```

CREATE OR REPLACE MODEL `bicycles.first_model`
OPTIONS(model_type='LINEAR_REG', l2_reg=0.2) AS
SELECT
start_station_name AS start_station,
address AS location_start_station,
#EXTRACT(HOUR FROM start_time) AS hourofday,
COUNT(*) as label
FROM
`bigquery-public-data.austin_bikeshare.bikeshare_stations`
FULL OUTER JOIN `bigquery-public-data.austin_bikeshare.bikeshare_trips` ON `bigquery-public-
data.austin_bikeshare.bikeshare_stations`.station_id=`bigquery-public-data.austin_bikeshare.bikeshare_trips`.start_station_id
WHERE DATE(start_time) > '2016-01-01' AND (start_time) < '2017-01-01'
GROUP BY start_station, location_start_station
ORDER BY start_station, location_start_station

```

- Second model:

#standardSQL

```

CREATE OR REPLACE MODEL `bicycles.second_model`

```

```

OPTIONS(model_type='LINEAR_REG', l2_reg=0.2) AS
SELECT
start_station_name AS start_station,
subscriber_type AS subscriber,
address AS location_start_station,
duration_minutes AS duration,
#EXTRACT(HOUR FROM start_time) AS hourofday,
COUNT(*) as label
FROM
`bigquery-public-data.austin_bikeshare.bikeshare_stations`
FULL OUTER JOIN `bigquery-public-data.austin_bikeshare.bikeshare_trips` ON `bigquery-public-
data.austin_bikeshare.bikeshare_stations`.station_id=`bigquery-public-data.austin_bikeshare.bikeshare_trips`.start_station_id
WHERE DATE(start_time) > '2016-01-01' AND (start_time) < '2017-01-01'
GROUP BY start_station, location_start_station, subscriber_type, duration_minutes
ORDER BY start_station, location_start_station

```

Evaluation of the second model:

```

#standardSQL
SELECT
*
FROM
ml.EVALUATE(MODEL `bicycles.second_model`, (
SELECT
start_station_name AS start_station,
subscriber_type AS subscriber,
address AS location_start_station,
#EXTRACT(HOUR FROM start_time) AS hourofday,
COUNT(*) as label
FROM
`bigquery-public-data.austin_bikeshare.bikeshare_stations`
FULL OUTER JOIN `bigquery-public-data.austin_bikeshare.bikeshare_trips` ON `bigquery-public-
data.austin_bikeshare.bikeshare_stations`.station_id=`bigquery-public-data.austin_bikeshare.bikeshare_trips`.start_station_id

```

```
WHERE DATE(start_time) > '2018-01-01' AND (start_time) < '2019-01-01'
```

```
GROUP BY start_station, location_start_station, subscriber_type
```

```
ORDER BY start_station, location_start_station))
```

Prediction of the second model:

From medium blog

Integrate with machine learning APIs:

- To create a service account, run the following account:

```
gcloud iam service-accounts create my-sa-123 --display-name "my service account"
```

What worked:

- Create a service account and add roles to it, just after creation.
- Then from keys create a json file and, create API key and export it as a variable.

After finalizing the script and getting all the results from it you can create a query in the “BigQuery” to get the language that occurred the most

The script by now

```
# Dataset: image_classification_dataset
```

```
# Table name: image_text_detail
```

```
import os
```

```
import sys
```

```
# Import Google Cloud Library modules
```

```
from google.cloud import storage, bigquery, language, vision, translate_v2
```

```
if ('GOOGLE_APPLICATION_CREDENTIALS' in os.environ):
```

```
if (not os.path.exists(os.environ['GOOGLE_APPLICATION_CREDENTIALS'])):
```

```
print ("The GOOGLE_APPLICATION_CREDENTIALS file does not exist.\n")
```

```
exit()
```

```
else:
```

```
print ("The GOOGLE_APPLICATION_CREDENTIALS environment variable is not defined.\n")
```

```
exit()
```

```
if len(sys.argv)<3:
```

```
print('You must provide parameters for the Google Cloud project ID and Storage bucket')
```

```
print ('python3 '+sys.argv[0]+ '[PROJECT_NAME] [BUCKET_NAME]')
```

```
exit()
```

```
project_name = sys.argv[1]
```

```
bucket_name = sys.argv[2]
```

```
# Set up our GCS, BigQuery, and Natural Language clients
```

```
storage_client = storage.Client()
```

```
bq_client = bigquery.Client(project=project_name)
```

```
nl_client = language.LanguageServiceClient()
```

```
# Set up client objects for the vision and translate_v2 API Libraries
```

```
vision_client = vision.ImageAnnotatorClient()
```

```
translate_client = translate_v2.Client()
```

```
# Setup the BigQuery dataset and table objects
```

```
dataset_ref = bq_client.dataset('image_classification_dataset')
```

```
dataset = bigquery.Dataset(dataset_ref)
```

```
table_ref = dataset.table('image_text_detail')
```

```
table = bq_client.get_table(table_ref)
```

```
# Create an array to store results data to be inserted into the BigQuery table
```

```
rows_for_bq = []
```

```
# Get a list of the files in the Cloud Storage Bucket
```

```
files = storage_client.bucket(bucket_name).list_blobs()
```

```
bucket = storage_client.bucket(bucket_name)
```

```
print('Processing image files from GCS. This will take a few minutes..')
```

```
# Process files from Cloud Storage and save the result to send to BigQuery
```

```
for file in files:
```

```
if file.name.endswith('.jpg') or file.name.endswith('.png'):
```

```
file_content = file.download_as_string()
```

```
# TBD: Create a Vision API image object called image_object
```

```
image_object = vision.Image(content=file_content)
```

```
# Ref: https://googleapis.dev/python/vision/latest/gapic/v1/types.html#google.cloud.vision\_v1.types.Image
```

```
# TBD: Detect text in the image and save the response data into an object called response
```

```
response = vision_client.label_detection(image=image_object)
```

```
labels = response.label_annotations
```

```
# create translation-request.json file manually
```

```
# run this one to translate the contents of the ocr-respons.txt file to the target language
```

```
# STR=$(jq .responses[0].textAnnotations[0].description ocr-response.txt) && STR="${STR/\"/\"}" && sed -i  
"s|your_text_here|${STR}|g" translation-request.json
```

```
# to call the translation API run:
```

```
# curl -s -X POST -H "Content-Type: application/json" --data-binary @translation-request.json  
https://translation.googleapis.com/language/translate/v2?key=\${API\_KEY} -o translation-response.json
```

```
# Ref:
```

```
https://googleapis.dev/python/vision/latest/gapic/v1/api.html#google.cloud.vision\_v1.ImageAnnotatorClient  
.document\_text\_detection
```

```
# Save the text content found by the vision API into a variable called text_data
```

```
text_data = response.text_annotations[0].description
```

```
# Save the text detection response data in <filename>.txt to cloud storage
```

```
file_name = file.name.split('.')[0] + '.txt'
```

```
blob = bucket.blob(file_name)
```

```
# Upload the contents of the text_data string variable to the Cloud Storage file
```

```
blob.upload_from_string(text_data, content_type='text/plain')
```

```
# Extract the description and locale data from the response file
```

```
# into variables called desc and locale
```

```
# using response object properties e.g. response.text_annotations[0].description
```

```
desc = response.text_annotations[0].description
```

```
locale = response.text_annotations[0].locale
```

```
# TBD: Save the description as the translated text into target_language eg. 'en', 'fr', and 'ja' according to the lab manual.
```

```
if locale == "":
```

```
    translated_text = desc
```

```
else:
```

```
    translate(target_language='english', format_='text')
```

```
# TBD: According to the target language pass the description data to the translation API
```

```
# ref:
```

```
https://googleapis.dev/python/translation/latest/client.html#google.cloud.translate\_v2.client.Client.translate
```

```
# Set the target_language locale to according to the lab activity)
```

```
translated_text = translation['translatedText']
```

```
print(translated_text)
```

```
# if there is response data save the original text read from the image,
```

```
# the locale, translated text, and filename
```

```
if len(response.text_annotations) > 0:
```

```
    rows_for_bq.append((desc, locale, translated_text, file.name))
```

```
print('Writing Vision API image data to BigQuery...')
```

```
# Write original text, locale and translated text to BQ
```

```
# TBD: When the script is working uncomment the next line to upload results to BigQuery
```

```
errors = bq_client.insert_rows(table, rows_for_bq)
```

```
assert errors == []
```